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The role of tutoring in higher education and improving the student's academic success

Abstract. Tutoring is a part of the university teaching-learning process and is a basic strategy for improving the student's academic success and professional goals. This article reviews the process of implementing tutors action plans in Urganch State University. The training and functions of tutors, the recognition of the tutoring task and the tools available to tutors at in Urganch State University are described.

Keywords. Tutor, tutorial action plan, academic success, professional goals, lifelong learning.

Аннотация. Тьютор является частью процесса преподавания и обучения в университете и представляет собой базовую стратегию для улучшения академических успехов студента и достижения профессиональных целей. В данной статье рассматривается процесс реализации планов действий тьюторов в Ургенчском государственном университете. Описаны подготовка и функции тьюторов, признание тьюторской задачи и инструменты, доступные тьюторам в Ургенчском государственном университете.

Ключевые слова. Тьютор план действий по обучению, успехи в учебе, профессиональные цели, обучение на протяжении всей жизни.

Annotatsiya. Tyutorlik universitet o'qitish jarayonining bir qismi bo'lib, talabanning akademik muvaffaqiyati va kasbiy maqsadlarini oshirishning asosiy strategiyasidir. Ushbu maqolada Urganch davlat universitetida tyutorlar ish rejalarini amalga oshirish jarayoni ko'rib chiqiladi. Urganch davlat universitetida tyutorlarning tayyorgarligi va vazifalari, tyutorlar vazifasini tan olish va tyutorlar uchun mavjud vositalar tasvirlangan.

Kalit so'zlar. Tyutor, o'quv rejasi, akademik muvaffaqiyat, professional maqsadlar, umrbod ta'lim.

Tutors can be full-time lecturers who express an interest in becoming involved in tutoring. They have to have social and communication skills and have taught on the degree their tutees are studying. Tutors can also, master's degree or doctorate (peer mentoring) who have enough time and the appropriate social and communicative skills. These peer mentoring initiatives have become widely adopted across uzbek universities as a way of integrating students into the higher education system. Tutors are assigned jointly by the faculty or school, and the department.

- Facilitate the integration of students into university.
- Assist the students in their academic work.
- Help students solve problems related to academic and university life.
- Facilitate the student's personal and professional progress.
- Help the student in his/her transition to the professional world.
- Tutors must call students to at least three individual tutorial sessions and have documentary evidence of the tutoring. They must also take part in tutor training, in follow-up meetings and in evaluating mentoring.

If one considers the environment surrounding higher education and changes in the roles demanded of higher education, the following sorts of key words come up regarding education reform in developing countries:

- Diversification of higher education institutions
- Promotion of lifelong learning
- Expansion of higher education and rectifying of inequities among groups
- Distance education and regional education through the application of information and communication technology
- Evaluation of higher education institutions and improvement of quality
- Networking of higher education institutions
- Cooperation with industry

- Promotion of private education
 - Diversification of funding for higher education
 - Governance, university self-government, and academic freedom
- Touching upon these actual approaches to higher education reform, Improvement of Educational Activities, Strengthening of Research Function, Promotion of Contributions to Society, and Improvement of Management.

The central function of higher education is education. Through educational activities, human resources necessary for socio-economic development are turned out for society and, for individuals, opportunities in higher education that match individual needs and abilities are offered-the objectives of higher education institutions. Thus, the improvement of educational activities in higher education is important. As directions for improvement, first, by diversifying higher education institutions, broader access can be secured and diverse needs in higher education can be responded to. Second, the quality of higher education must also be improved. Third, planning for the expansion of higher education opportunities for women and other vulnerable groups must take place so that inequities in higher education can be rectified.